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Prenatal Development of Parathyroid Glands of Buffalo

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The parathyroid glands are derivatives of the embryonic pharyngeal region. The embryonic development parathyroid glands are studied in hamster (Ackerman and Knouff, 1964) and dog (Hendrickx, 1964). However, such information is not available for buffaloes. Hence, a comprehensive study on histogenesis of parathyroid glands was undertaken in buffalo.

Materials and Methods

18 buffalo fetuses were used for the present study and their CRL (crown rump length) varied from 9 cm to 31 cm. Buffalo fetuses of different gestational ages were collected from non-descript buffalo calves sacrificed in and around Tirupati, Andhra Pradesh. The CRL was measured as a

curved line along the vertebral column between the most anterior part of frontal bone to the ischiatic tuberosity (Edward, 1965). The approximate age of the foetus was determined on the basis of their CRL by using Soliman's formulae (1975). After measuring the CRL, the small embryos of less than 6 cm CRL were fixed as a whole. From large embryos thyroid and parathyroid glands were dissected out and fixed in 10 percent neutral buffered formalin. The fixed tissues were processed for paraffin blocks by acetone benzene schedule. The paraffin sections of 5-6 μ m were stained with Mayer's haematoxylin and eosin for normal histomorphology (Luna, 1968).

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Fig. Semilogarithmic plot of plasma levofloxacin concentrations versus time following single dose IV and oral administration at the rate of 10 mg/kg of bw in WLH layer birds. Each point represents Mean $\pm$ SE of 12 layer birds.

enrofloxacin, danofloxacin and pefloxacin reported in chicken. However clearance of levofloxacin was faster than ofloxacin (4.96 ml/min/kg) and ciprofloxacin (1.54 $\pm$ 0.16 ml/min/kg) in chickens and ducks, respectively. The apparent volume of distribution [$V_{d(\text{area})}$] of the drug was found to be 4.02 $\pm$ 0.08 l/kg, which is parallel to apparent volume of distribution of enrofloxacin (4.31 $\pm$ 0.15 l/kg) and pefloxacin (5.12 $\pm$ 0.78 l/kg) in chicken and ducks, respectively. Apparent volume of distribution of levofloxacin was greater than that of ofloxacin and ciprofloxacin reported in chickens.

Following oral administration of the drug, the peak plasma concentration of 0.92 $\pm$ 0.01 μ g/ml was observed at 2 h (T_{max}). The elimination half life (3.62 $\pm$ 0.12 h) and mean residence time of the drug (6.41 $\pm$ 0.13 h) following oral administration found in the present study were lower than the values reported with other fluoroquinolones in chickens and ducks. The apparent volume of distribution of the drug in the present study was higher than volume of distribution of enrofloxacin (5.94 $\pm$ 0.20 l/kg) and ofloxacin (2.16 l/kg) reported in chicken. Following oral administration, the systemic bioavailability of levofloxacin (71.61 $\pm$ 1.38%) in the present study was parallel to the bioavailability of ciprofloxacin (70.09 $\pm$ 9.8%)

reported in chickens. However, higher bioavailabilities of ofloxacin (110.01%), danofloxacin (99.2%) and enrofloxacin (89.2%) have been also reported in chickens. The results suggested that levofloxacin had favourable pharmacokinetics for oral administration in poultry.

The values for AUC/MIC and $C_{\text{max}}/\text{MIC}$ after oral administration were calculated using documented MIC values against gram-positive and gram-negative organisms. The MIC₉₀ of 0.03 and 0.06 μ g/ml of levofloxacin was taken into consideration for calculation of efficacy predictors for levofloxacin in poultry. The calculated value of $C_{\text{max}}/\text{MIC}$ (30.66 at MIC of 0.03 μ g/ml, 15.33 at MIC of 0.06 μ g/ml) and AUC/MIC (215.66 at MIC of 0.03 μ g/ml, 107.83 at MIC of 0.06 μ g/ml) indicated excellent clinical and bacteriological efficacy of levofloxacin in WLH layer birds.

Summary

Pharmacokinetics of levofloxacin was determined following single dose i/v and oral (po) administration at the dose rate of 10 mg/kg bw in White Leghorn (WLH) layer birds in a cross over design study. Drug concentration in plasma was determined by high performance liquid chromatography and the data obtained were subjected to non-compartmental analysis. Following single dose intravenous administration, the drug was rapidly distributed ($t_{1/2}$; 0.27 $\pm$ 0.01 h) and eliminated ($t_{1/2}$; 3.08 $\pm$ 0.05 h) from the body at the rate of 15.09 $\pm$ 0.21 ml/min/kg. Following oral administration, the drug was rapidly absorbed (C_{max} ; 0.92 $\pm$ 0.01 μ g/ml; T_{max} ; 2 h) and slowly eliminated ($t_{1/2}$; 3.62 $\pm$ 0.12 h) from body. The apparent volume of distribution [$V_{d(\text{area})}$], total body clearance (ClB) and mean residence time (MRT) following oral administration were 8.07 $\pm$ 0.24 L/kg, 25.82 $\pm$ 0.40 ml/min/kg and 6.41 $\pm$ 0.13 h, respectively. The oral bioavailability of levofloxacin was 71.61 $\pm$ 1.38%. Based on results obtained in the present study, levofloxacin can be administered through oral route in layer birds at 10 mg/kg repeated at 12 h.

Results and Discussion

In the present study 0.9 cm CRL (26 days) embryo was the youngest in which five pairs of pharyngeal pouches were noted between the brachial arches on the lateral wall of the pharyngeal entoderm. The last one of these (fifth) was small and appeared to be absorbed into the fourth pharyngeal pouch resulting in the formation of caudal pharyngeal pouch complex. The pharyngeal pouches in buffalo were numbered 1 to 4 in cephalocaudal sequence. Kingsbury (1936), Noden and De Lahunta (1985) in cattle and Prasad and Singh (1990) in goat stated that the fifth pharyngeal pouch never attained the morphological value of a definite pouch. The first and second pouches were small and shallower, whereas the third pouch was the largest of all.

The entoderm of the third pharyngeal pouch showed extensive proliferation of epithelial cells that led to formation of a common primordium for both parathyroid and thymus at 1.2 cm CRL (28 days) stage. The dorsal part of this primordium was differentiated into a solid bar of tissue that transformed into external parathyroid glands. Eurell and Frappier (2007) noted the entodermal origin of parathyroid gland in domestic animals. This parathyroid tissue was referred to as parathyroid 3 which denoted its origin (Latshaw, 1987) and it was located at the origin of occipital artery. The ventral part of the primordium was initially tubular and transformed into definitive thymus in the subsequent stage of development. Latshaw (*loc. cit.*) in domestic animals reported dorsal solid and ventral tubular portions in the primordium of third pharyngeal pouch. The entodermal cells of the dorsal diverticulum of fourth pharyngeal pouch developed in a manner similar to their counter parts of the 3rd pouch that led to formation of parathyroid 4 called as internal parathyroids. They were placed cranial to the thyroid gland. The ultimobranchial bodies were developed from the caudal pharyngeal pouch at 2.5 cm CRL (40 days, Fig. 2).

The parathyroid and thymic primordial lost their connection with the pharynx at this stage. According to Hendrickx (*loc. cit.*), the connection between the pharynx and primordium of the third pharyngeal pouch was lost between 26 days to 28 days of gestation in dog. Later the two primordials were separated from each other and migrated to their definitive locations.

The epithelial cells of the parathyroid primordium were recognizably different in structure from those of thymic primordium. The parathyroid primordium appeared stained lighter than the thymic primordium and was devoid of lymphocytes. The parathyroid 3 primordium was placed dorsal to the thymic primordium. The parathyroid 4 was placed dorsal to the thyroid primordium and 3rd aortic arch and maintained its integrity as caudal or internal parathyroids. The parathyroid gland of 31.0 cm CRL (143 days) buffalo foetus showed a distinct connective tissue capsule with large number of collagen fibres.

In the present investigation, two types of cells were noted in the parathyroid gland viz, principal or chief cells and oxyphil cells as reported by Eurell and Frappier (*loc. cit.*) in domestic animals. The principal cells were designated as active and inactive cells. The active

Fig 1. Photomicrograph of buffalo foetus of 1.2 cm CRL (28 days) showing pharynx (Ph), neural tube (Nt) and a common primordium for parathyroid (Pt) and thymus (T) - Haematoxylin and Eosin x 200.

Fig 2. Photomicrograph of buffalo foetus of 2.5 cm CRL (40 days) showing developing parathyroid (Pt), thyroid (Th), thymus (T), oesophagus (O), trachea (Tr), ultimobranchial body (U) and aortic arch III (A) - Haematoxylin and Eosin x 100.

Fig 3. Photomicrograph of buffalo foetus of 31.0 cm CRL (143 days) showing chief cells (C) and oxyphil cells (O) in parathyroid gland - Haematoxylin and Eosin x 400.

cells were more darkly stained than the inactive cells. The chief cells were round to polyhedral in shape and had round nuclei. The oxyphil cells were larger than the chief cells and contained granular cytoplasm. The active (dark) and inactive (light) cells were distributed randomly in buffalo, while in sheep and goat light cells occupied the periphery of the gland and the dark cells were observed at the centre.

Summary

In buffalo foetus five pharyngeal pouches were noted at 0.9 cm CRL (26 days). The 3rd pharyngeal pouch showed a common primordium for parathyroid 3 and thymus at 1.2 cm CRL (28 days). The dorsal part of this primordium was differentiated into a solid bar of tissue that transformed into external parathyroid glands whereas, internal parathyroid glands were developed from 4th pharyngeal pouches. At 2.5 cm CRL (40 days) parathyroid and thymic primordia lost their connection with the pharynx. The parathyroid primordium was stained lighter than the thymic primordium. A distinct

connective tissue capsule was noted around the parathyroid gland in buffalo at 31.0 cm CRL (143 days) and at this stage two types of cells were noted in the parathyroid gland, viz, principal or chief cells and oxyphil cells.

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